

Effect of Structural Changes on Dyes derived from Naphthoxazoles

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In the present investigation several *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their corresponding aza and diaza analogues, merocyanines and unsymmetrical cyanines have been prepared from alpha and beta-naphthoxazoles. The absorption data of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their aza and diaza analogues have been used to evaluate the effect on absorption of the replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ and to calculate the relative order of basicities of alpha- and beta-naphthoxazoles in the light of Forster's rule. The absorption data of merocyanines and unsymmetrical cyanines have also been used to determine the relative order of acidities and basicities of various ketomethylene compounds and basic heterocyclic nuclei.

The present work describes the preparation of some *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes, their aza and diaza analogues, merocyanines and unsymmetrical cyanines derived from 2-methyl and 2-methyl mercapto alpha- and beta-naphthoxazoles. Their absorption spectra have been studied and utilised in the evaluation of the effect of the replacement of $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$ by $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ in the chromophoric chain on the absorption of these dyes. The relative order of acidities of ketomethylene compounds and of the basicities of the 2-methyl quaternary salts have been evaluated with the help of the absorption data of merocyanines and unsymmetrical cyanines respectively.

For the preparation of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their aza analogues, 2-methyl alpha- and beta-naphthoxazoles were necessary and were prepared by standard methods¹⁻⁵. The quaternary salts were prepared by heating 2-methyl naphthoxazoles with methyl iodide in a sealed tube.

The dialkylamino styryl compounds (I, X=CH) were prepared by condensing the quaternary salts with *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde in acetic anhydride.

(I) X=CH or N

The aza analogues (I, X=N) of the dialkylamino styryl dyes were prepared by heating the quaternary salts with *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline in the presence of acetic anhydride.

1. Hodgson, Kilner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 807.
2. Fischer, Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 963.
3. C. S. Marvel and P. K. Porter, *Org. Syn. Coll.*, Vol. I, p. 411.
4. J. B. Conant and B. B. Corson, *Org. Syn. Coll.*, Vol. II, p. 33.
5. Fischer, Hamer et al, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 963.

For preparing the diaza analogues, 2-methyl mercapto alpha- and beta-naphthoxazoles were prepared by known methods⁶⁻⁷. Their quaternary salts were then condensed with 60% hydrazine hydrate giving the corresponding hydrazone (II)

The hydrazones were condensed separately with

- (i) dimethyl aniline
- (ii) diethyl aniline
- (iii) N-N-dimethyl alpha-naphthylamine

in 1N hydrochloric acid in the presence of a little amount of ferrous sulphate and 30% hydrogen peroxide to give the diaza analogues of these dyes by slight modification of the method of Hunig⁸. The following mechanism of the condensation is suggested :

The diaza analogues (which may also be regarded as azo dyes) were also prepared by condensing the hydrazones with (i) 2-hydroxy 4-phenyl thiazole, (ii) 8-hydroxy quinoline exactly in the above manner. The mechanism of the condensation is same as described above.

The diaza analogues were prepared with a view to study the dyeing properties of these dyes for cotton fibres.

The absorption maxima of the *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their corresponding aza analogues are given in the Table-I.

TABLE I

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of X and Y and their absorption maxima in m μ .			Bathochromic shift observed in m μ .		
	CH=CH a	CH=N b	N=N c	b-a	c-b	c-a
alpha naphthoxazole	485	520	580	35	60	95
beta naphthoxazole	487	525	580	38	55	93

6. R. D. Desai and R. F. Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 327.

7. J. D. Kendall et al, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1505.

8. Hunig et al, *Annalen*, 1957, 57, 609.

The replacement of =CH- by =N- in the chromophoric chain in *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes is expected to give rise to bathochromic shift on the basis of Forster's Rule⁹. Here the most likely excited structure involves \ominus -X⁺, as in case of beta anilino vinyl derivatives and their aza analogues. Since \ominus -CH⁺ is more stable than \ominus -N⁺, the replacement of =CH- by =N- will raise the energy of the inter-auxochromic ionic excited structure. So according to Forster's Rule which states that the absorption maxima of the dye will increase with the decreasing tendency of the chain of atoms lying between the auxochromes to take up the characteristic charge, bathochromic shift will be observed. When both the =C H-groups are replaced by =N-, giving rise to -N=N-, the characteristic charge is again \ominus -X⁺ as shown below.

So when (X=CH) is replaced by N i.e. (X=N), on account of decreased stability of \ominus -N⁺, relative to \ominus -CH⁺, the tendency of the chromophoric chain to take up the characteristic charge is decreased and hence a bathochromic shift is observed. Actually bathochromic shifts are observed by replacement of -CH=CH- by -CH=N- and -N=N- in all cases (Table-I).

Since in case of *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their aza analogues the most likely excited structure involves \ominus -X⁺ and not \ominus -X⁻, the significance of the structure will thus decrease with increasing electron repelling properties i.e. the increasing basicity of the heterocyclic nucleus 'A'. It therefore, follows that a larger

bathochromic shift will be observed in a compound derived from a more weakly basic nucleus.

Turning to our experimental results in the Table-I it is seen that bathochromic shift observed in case of beta-naphthoxazole is more than that in case of alpha-naphthoxazole (Table I, column 5) and hence alpha-naphthoxazole is more basic than beta naphthoxazole.

Merocyanines ($n=0$) were prepared by treatment of the 2-mercapto methyl para-toluene sulphonates of alpha-and beta-naphthoxazoles with the ketomethylene compounds in acetic anhydride and triethylamine; and the merocyanines ($n=1$) were prepared by condensing the acetanilidovinyl compounds obtained from the oxazoles with various ketomethylene compounds in alcohol and triethylamine.

The absorption maxima of the merocyanines have been determined and with the help of these data, the deviations of the individual merocyanines have been calculated. According to Forster's Rule⁹, the greater the deviation, the lower is the acidity. Thus with the help of the deviation data, the relative acidity of various acidic nuclei used have been evaluated (Table-II).

The relative acidities conform to the following sequence :

Iso-oxazolone > Oxazolone > Thio-thiazolone > Thiobarbituric acid and benz-coumarin > Pyrazolone > Rhodanine > Thiohydantoin.

TABLE II

Absorption maxima and deviation of the dimethin merocyanines.

Nature of the nucleus B	Sym. of A	Nucleus 'A'				Nucleus 'B'					
		Oxonol of B	Cal. λ max.	Obs. λ max.	Deviation	Sym. of A	Oxonol of B	Cal. λ max.	Obs. λ max.	Deviation	
		Nucleus A=alpha-naphthoxazole					Nucleus B=beta-naphthoxazole				
Pyrazolone	515	438	476.5	450	26.5	515	438	476.5	447	29.5	
Rhodanine	515	552	533.5	506	27.5	515	552	533.5	501	32.5	
Thiobarbituric acid	515	460	487.5	475	12.5	515	460	487.5	475	12.5	
Iso-oxazolone	515	435	475	510	-35	515	435	475	508	-33	
Thiohydantoin	515	520	517.5	490	27.5	515	520	517.5	485	32.5	
Oxazolone	515	480	495.5	505	-9.5	515	480	495.5	503	-7.5	
Thio-thiazolone	515	510	512.5	505	7.5	515	510	512.5	505	7.5	
Benz-coumarin	515	430	472.5	460	12.5	515	430	472.5	460	12.5	

TABLE IV

Absorption maxima and deviation of unsymmetrical cyanines derived from naphthoxazoles.

Nature of the nucleus A	Sym. of A	Sym. of B	Cal. λ max	Obs. λ max	Devn.	Sym. of A	Sym. of B	Cal. λ max	Obs. λ max	Devn.
	Nucleus B = α naphthoxazole					Nucleus A = β naphthoxazole				
4 : 5 diphenyl thiazole	585	515	550	544	6	585	515	550	544	6
4- <i>p</i> -chloro phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	587	515	551	548	3	587	515	551	550	1
4- <i>p</i> -methyl phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	595	515	555	552	3	595	515	555	554	1
4- <i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	597	515	556	553	3	597	515	556	555	1
4- <i>p</i> -fluorophenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	590	515	552.5	550	2.5	590	515	552.5	530	2.5
4- <i>p</i> (2'-5'-dimethyl) phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	593	515	554	554	0	593	515	554	554	0
4-phenyl 5- <i>p</i> -nitro phenyl thiazole	602	515	558.5	555	3.5	602	515	558.5	556	2.5
4-phenyl 5-(2'-4'-dichloro) phenyl thiazole	576	515	545.5	550	-4.5	576	515	545.5	550	-4.5
4-phenyl-5-(2'-chloro) phenyl thiazole	576	515	545.5	548	-2.5	576	515	545.5	548	-2.5
4-phenyl thiazole	565	515	540	535	5	565	515	540	535	5

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(2-acetanilido vinyl) alpha-naphthoxazole methiodide :—

2-methyl alpha-naphthoxazole methiodide (3.25 gm) and diphenyl formamidine (2.2 gms) were refluxed in 20 cc of acetic anhydride for 10 minutes. The reaction product was cooled. The solid which separated was washed with ether followed by a little benzene and acetone and was finally crystallised from alcohol.

Yield - 75%, M.P. - 260°

(Found C : 56.03 ; H 3.98%. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{I}$ requires C : 56.17 ; H 4.04%)

2-(2-acetanilido vinyl)-beta naphthoxazole methiodide :—

It was prepared as above using 2-methyl beta-naphthoxazole methiodide (3.25 gm) and diphenyl formamidine (2.2 gms) in 20 cc of acetic anhydride and finally crystallised from alcohol.

Yield - 70%, M.P. - 217°

(Found ; C 56.10 ; H 3.96%. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{I}$ requires C : 56.17 ; H 4.04%)

2-(p-dimethylamino styryl)-3-methyl alpha naphthoxazolium iodide :-

alpha-naphthoxazole methiodide (0.31 gm) and *p*-dimethylamino benzaldehyde (0.15 gm) in 10 cc of acetic anhydride were refluxed for 10 minutes and cooled. The solid which separated was washed with ether and finally crystallised from alcohol.

The other *p*-dialkylamino styryl dyes and their aza analogues (prepared by taking *p*-nitroso dimethyl aniline instead of *p*-dimethyl-amino benzaldehyde) were prepared by the method similar to above.

Their analytical data and m. p. etc. are given in Table-V.

TABLE V

Nature of the nucleus "A"	Nature of X	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max	%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
alpha naphthoxazole	CH	60	231	485	57.52	57.64	4.97	5.02
beta naphthoxazole	CH	60	225	487	57.49	57.64	4.89	5.02
alpha naphthoxazole	N	50	>250	520	54.73	54.90	4.76	4.80
beta naphthoxazole	N	50	>250	525	54.69	54.90	4.69	4.80

Diaza analogues of p-dialkylamino styryl dyes :-

Alpha-naphthoxazole N-methyl hydrazone (0.1 gm) and dimethyl aniline (0.16 gm) were dissolved in 1N hydrochloric acid (8 cc) and ferrous sulphate (3 mg.) was added. The solution was cooled to 30° and hydrogen peroxide (1.87 gm, 30 Vol.) was added when the dye formed quickly. After 30 minutes formic acid (15 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was heated to 90° on a water bath. After five minutes the solution was filtered and to the filtrate sodium iodide (0.5 gm) dissolved in minimum volume of water was added. The dye separated out as iodide on cooling. It was filtered and washed with a cold solution of sodium iodide and finally crystallised from chloro benzene, M. P. >250°, Yield - 30%. (Found : C. 52.15, H, 4.08, C₂₀H₁₉N₄OI requires C, 52.40 ; H, 4.15).

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the different diaza compounds derived from alpha- and beta- naphthoxazoles with dimethyl aniline, diethyl aniline, N-N-dimethyl alpha naphthylamine, 8-hydroxy quinoline and 4-phenyl-2-hydroxy thiazole are given in Table-VI.

TABLE VI

Diaza compounds derived from uagthoxazoles

Nature of the nucleus 'A'	Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Yield %	M. P. °C	λ max	%Carbon		%Hydrogen	
					Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Alpha naphthoxazole	Dimethyl aniline	30	>250	580	52.15	52.40	4.08	4.15
"	Diethyl aniline	25	193	585	54.27	54.33	4.34	4.74
"	N-N-Dimethyl alpha-naphthylamine	35	196	585	56.36	56.66	4.09	4.13
"	8-Hydroxy quinoline	39	190	480	52.18	52.29	2.96	3.11
"	2-hydroxy 4-phenyl thiazole	28	182	475	48.85	49.03	2.86	2.92
Beta naphthoxazole	Dimethyl aniline	29	181	580	52.31	52.40	4.07	4.15
"	Diethyl aniline	32	181 (d)	585	54.21	54.33	4.63	4.74
"	N-N-Dimethyl alpha-naphthylamine	35	169	585	56.52	56.66	4.03	4.13
"	8-Hydroxy quinoline	40	172	480	52.17	52.29	3.10	3.11
"	2-Hydroxy 4-phenyl thiazole	30	148	475	49.10	49.03	2.86	2.91

'd' denotes decomposition.

5-(3-methyl alpha-naphthoxazolin-2-ylidene) 3-phenyl rhodanine :—

2-methyl mercapto alpha-naphthoxazole metho-*p*-toluene sulphonate (0.35 g. and 3-phenyl rhodanine (0.2 g.) were refluxed in distilled acetic anhydride (5 cc) in the presence of one drop of triethylamine for 10 minutes. The compound separated after adding water in cold and was finally crystallised from ethanol, m. p.-156°, yield-55% (Found : C, 64.55 ; H, 3.49. $C_{21}H_{14}O_2N_2S_2$ requires C, 64.62 ; H, 3.58%).

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the related merocyanines ($n=0$) derived from various ketomethylene compounds are given in the Table-VII.

5-(3-methyl-2-alpha-naphthoxazolinyldiene) ethylidene-3-phenyl rhodanine :—

2-(acetanilido vinyl) alpha-naphthoxazole methiodide (0.47 g.) and 3-phenyl rhodanine (0.2 g.) were refluxed in 10 cc of alcohol and 2 drops of triethylamine for 10 minutes. The products separated after cooling, was filtered and finally crystallised from alcohol. Yield - 55%, m.p.-129°. (Found : C, 66.29 ; H, 3.79. $C_{23}H_{16}O_2N_2S_2$ requires C, 66.34 ; H, 3.85%).

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the related merocyanines ($n=1$) derived from different ketomethylene compounds are given in the Table-VII.

(3-methyl-benzothiazole) (3-methyl-alpha-naphthoxazole)-2'-2'-trimethin cyanine iodide :—

2-(2-acetanilido vinyl)-alpha-naphthoxazole methiodide (0.47 gm), benzothiazole methiodide (0.29 gm) in 10 ml of ethanol and two drops of triethylamine were

TABLE IX

*Unsymmetrical cyanines derived from naphthoxazole
and different 4 : 5 diaryl thiazoles.*

Nucleus A	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max	Found		Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max	Found	
				Calcd.	Calcd.				Calcd.	Calcd.
				Nucleus B=alpha naphthoxazole					Nucleus B=beta naphthoxazole	
4 : 5 : diphenyl thiazole	60	160	544	C : 61.32 H : 3.51	61.53 3.76	60	148	544	C : 61.49 H : 3.18	61.53 3.76
4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	73	210	548	C : 58.41 H : 3.67	58.62 3.78	47	235	550	C : 58.29 H : 3.47	58.62 3.78
4- <i>p</i> -methyl phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	82	222	552	C : 62.18 H : 4.20	62.54 4.39	73	198	554	C : 62.32 H : 4.18	62.54 4.39
4- <i>p</i> -methoxy phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	54	163	553	C : 60.12 H : 4.10	60.45 4.28	56	210	555	C : 60.29 H : 4.17	60.45 4.28
4- <i>p</i> -fluoro phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	86	140	550	C : 60.01 H : 3.23	60.19 3.87	46	>250	550	C : 60.12 H : 3.69	60.19 3.87
4-(2'-5'-dimethyl phenyl 5-phenyl thiazole	30	225	554	C : 62.96 H : 4.18	63.05 4.45	35	240	554	C : 62.91 H : 4.39	63.05 4.45
4-phenyl 5- <i>p</i> -nitro phenyl thiazole	39	80	555	C : 57.36 H : 3.46	57.67 3.72	75	225	556	C : 57.51 H : 3.31	57.67 3.72
4-phenyl 5-(2'-4'- dichloro) phenyl thiazole	50	228	548	C : 55.42 H : 3.13	55.61 3.43	80	220	548	C : 55.48 H : 3.23	55.61 3.43
4-phenyl-5-(2'-chloro) phenyl thiazole	57	167	550	C : 58.39 H : 3.26	58.62 3.78	75	240	550	C : 58.37 H : 3.62	58.62 3.78

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